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A Communication Toolkit for ARDC Co-Investment Projects

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About This Toolkit

Target audience: This toolkit is designed for those leading and supporting ARDC co-investment projects.

Purpose: This toolkit has been created to help you develop a communication strategy throughout your project lifecycle - from establishment to building and launch phases.

Together we have co-invested a significant amount of time, effort and resources in developing world-class research data assets, tools, platforms and/or infrastructure. To maximise the return on all that investment, we need to tell researchers and other key audiences about what we have developed and how they can use it. We all want to see the benefits of our projects to research, and for all Australians, to continue well into the future and having a strong communication plan will help us to ensure this happens.

Your communication strategy will help keep internal and external stakeholders well informed about the project, its long-term impact, and raise awareness and recognition amongst the wider community.

Every project has varied levels of access to communication and marketing professionals within the project or at partner institutions. If you have communication resources, we recommend you talk to them, and use this toolkit to help you prepare for conversations about what communication support you need for your project. If you don't have any resources, this can help you scope what you can achieve within your project to meet your communication objectives.

This toolkit is designed to be a living document that you update regularly throughout your project, and use as a source of ideas and strategies to communicate your research data asset, tool or platform.

How to use this toolkit:

1. Read this toolkit through once to get ideas for what you need to do (expected time: 30 mins)
2. Workshop sections of the toolkit with your team (2 workshops, ~50 mins each)
3. Write and edit your communication plan (expected time: 1-2 hours)

Toolkit outcomes:

1. A communication strategy and plan for your project
2. Target audiences identified
3. Words to use when talking or writing about your project with your target audiences
4. Communication tactics and channels for communicating with your target audiences

Prior knowledge needed: You will need a good understanding of your project purpose and what it will achieve, and your target audience groups.

Workshop recommendations:

- Please make a copy of this document for your team. You can then use this document as a collaborative Google doc online to work together on it
- Prior to Workshop 1: Fill out the project information, review the document to get ideas for communication
- Workshop 1 - go through the section “Create your Communication Strategy”.
 - After Workshop 1, tidy up the information you collected, and share it with your team to get consensus that the strategy looks correct
 - Write your Project Description using the key messages you’ve developed.
 - Review the section on “Communication tactics and channels” to develop ideas for the communication plan.
- Workshop 2 - work on ideas for the section “Create your Communication Plan”. Come up with ideas of how to communicate to your audiences at key milestones of your project.
 - Tidy up the plan and prioritise the plan, assigning items to team members to lead.

Project Information

Summary project information to support communication activities. You should already have this information at hand. It will help us create a communication strategy.

Summary	Details
Project name	
Project start and end date	
Project objectives	
What does success look like for the project?	
Key people involved - name and organisation	
Comms lead for this plan	
Links to webpages, articles or other online materials about your project. <i>Eg. the ARDC project page</i>	

Create Your Communication Strategy

This section will guide your communication plan and activities.

Sections	Information
<p>Communication Objectives</p> <p>Focus on your end goal and actions you want your target audience to take. e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To raise awareness with potential users... To drive <an action such as 'traffic to a website', sign up for more information, attend a webinar> To get researchers using our platform/data asset To convince administrators to support our projects (by investing, in-kind contributions, funding proposals, etc) To forge more partnerships To increase impact by getting attention from stakeholders 	
<p>Target Audiences</p> <p>Who do you want to target with your communication efforts to achieve your objectives? Who do you need to communicate with so that your project will be:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Used by people 2. Supported into the future <p>You may have:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Primary target audiences 2. Secondary/indirect audience group 	-

Sections	Information
<p>Identifying your audiences will help you craft messages that appeal to them.</p> <p>E.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers in Australia who do xyz - University administrators who can fund our project - Xyz industry 	
<p>Key messages</p> <p>Key messages will be used across your communication materials - in presentations, on your website, in social media etc. It is the consistent set of messages you can agree on that suits your audiences.</p> <p>What do you want to say to your target audience to get them interested and involved?</p> <p>Put yourself in each of your target audience’s shoes and consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ What are the pain points in their research that your project will help with? ■ What information do they care about? ■ Write short, succinct sentences that appeal to your audience, using plain English. <p>e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - project purpose or objectives - Approval / Implementation / start / end / key dates - Benefits for researchers / society - Why should they care? - Call to action (what do you want the target audience to do?) 	

Sections	Information
<p>Communication Opportunities</p> <p>These are unique communication opportunities available to your project thanks to pre-existing relationships, partners, community involvement, etc.</p>	<p><i>e.g. the project leader has a strong following on social media a good media profile</i></p> <p><i>Person writes for The Conversation</i></p> <p><i>I have a strong relationship with X organisation, which has a strong media communications team</i></p> <p><i>I'm speaking at X conference</i></p>

Write Your Project Description

The sections below help you hone your messages about your project. These sections are similar to those on the new ARDC project pages. Consider who you wish to influence and talk to before you write this section. You may wish to make sure it speaks to both researchers and directors of research institutions.

EXAMPLES: ARDC projects have this basic information on their ARDC website pages. Some examples include: [A Research Software Agenda for Australia](#), [People Research Data Commons](#).

CSIRO also has excellent project pages that answer similar questions, for example: [Our Knowledge, Our Way guidelines](#), [A digital platform for gestational diabetes support](#), [Effects of trawling](#)

Sections	Information
<p>Project goal</p> <p>What is the overall problem your project will address?</p> <p>Why is this problem important?</p>	
<p>Project approach</p> <p>What will the project do to address this problem?</p> <p>What approach will it take?</p>	

Sections	Information
<p>What will be the outcome(s)?</p> <p>What results/things/reports will the project produce?</p> <p>What will be the impact on research/society/environment/economy?</p>	
<p>Project partners</p>	
<p>Who will benefit from this project?</p> <p>e.g.</p> <p>researchers who do ecological modelling</p> <p>Policy makers, decision makers who can use modelling to make decisions</p> <p>Research data managers at research institutions</p> <p>the Agricultural industry</p> <p>farmers</p>	

Communication Strategy On A Page

This is a summary of the sections above that you can save as a one-pager to print, share and refer to easily.

This section will guide your communication plan and activities.

[Project/Program Name] Communication Strategy			
Project Goal	Project Approach	Project Outcomes	Communication Objective
■	■	■	■
Target Audiences			
Key Messages For Each Target Audience			
Tools And Tactics To Reach Each Audience			

What to Consider When Crafting Your Communication Plan

To help you craft your communication plan, we recommend you read the following information on:

1. Communication opportunities at each project phase
2. Communication opportunities at specific project milestones
3. Communication tactics and channels you can use at these different points

This information will help you to create a communication plan that suits the different phases of your project and the resources you have available.

Communication Opportunities at Each Project Phase

Project Phase 1: Establish

Congratulations on securing co-investment from ARDC for your project! Once the contract is signed, you can launch your project to gain interest.

Goal in this phase:

- Connect with partners and your target audiences, including future users, sharing information on how to get involved now and in the future
- Engage with your institutional or organisational communications team - suggest announcing the new funding and launching the project. During the engagement, provide them with some key milestones for your project, and let them know when you'll be in touch around those to organise communication activities

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Possible communication activities:

1. Launch your project via an article or blog post in institutional/organisational/departmental news channels and the ARDC
2. Build your future user base by encouraging people to join your mailing list to receive updates on the project
3. Establish core communication channels, such as a mailing list, webpage or website, name and brand, social media
4. Create a list of potential communication channels for your audiences: newsletters, conferences, etc.

Project Phase 2: Build

In this phase, you'll be busy building your research infrastructure. Here are some ways to engage your future users and funders:

Goal for this phase:

1. Building your mailing list of interested people
2. Remind people that you exist
3. Get them involved if you can

Possible communication activities:

1. Invite people to be part of focus groups or beta testing
2. Speak about your project at industry and community events, webinars and conferences
3. Write updates about your project, publish them on your website and/or share them via email and social media
4. Present your pitch to potential future funders and supporters of your project
5. Build relationships with the communication teams at your partner institutions and explore communication opportunities.

Project Phase 3: Launch

The launch of your project outcomes is your time to shine! This is one of the most exciting times in your project from a communication perspective. It's a great reason to shout about your project via every possible communication channel you have. Your new piece of research infrastructure is only new for a very short period of time, and you want to capitalise on this momentous occasion.

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Goal for this phase:

1. Grow your user base
2. Engage potential future funders by articulating project impact
3. Implement and tell people about your sustainability strategy

Possible communication activities:

1. Media release/news article via partner communication channels, The Conversation article, ARDC article
2. Launch your outputs at a conference or event
3. Speak about your project at industry events, webinars and conferences
4. Conduct webinars and training sessions on your tool. Put recordings on YouTube and share them widely
5. Present your pitch to potential funders and supporters of your project

Communication Opportunities at Project Milestones

We can plan communication activities around public milestones such as beta testing, conference presentations, webinars (and recordings), launching the product, case studies demonstrating impact.

Create a simple list of project milestones. This will help inform your communication plan, which we will work on below.

e.g.

March 2022 - project approved by ARDC Board

April 2022 - webinar with key stakeholders

May 2022 - workshops/consultations

June 2022 - request for platform testers

August 2022 - conference presentation

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Jan 2023 - pilot outcomes

July 2023 - platform launch

Communication Tactics and Channels

Here is a guide to communication tactics and channels. As you read through this section, make a note of which ones sound the most useful for your team, considering your skills and capabilities. Also consider your audiences and how best to reach them.

These are the channels you could explore as ways to reach your audience.

If you're unsure, ask a few people from your target audience where they spend their time and how they get information.

For example:

- If your audience is neuroscientists, sponsoring or speaking at a neuroscience conference is a good channel
- For directors and business people, LinkedIn is a great channel
- For researchers in general, LinkedIn and relevant newsletters are a good channel
- For libraries, Listservs and Google Groups are good channels
- For government and policy makers, the media is a good channel
- For HDR students, Instagram and Snapchat are good channels

Website

Does your project need its own website? Creating a website means you must commit to updating it and maintaining it into the future. But it can also be a great launchpad for your platform, and a place to send people to find out more information and sign up to your mailing list.

Creating a website doesn't mean anyone will magically find you online. Google needs to index your site and recognise the content on it as relevant to the searcher. It can take a lot of work and content, and needs to be supported by a communications plan that will help send people to it.

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Here are some examples of ARDC-supported project websites:

- [EcoCommons](#) - a custom-built and designed website
- [WildObs](#) - Canva
- [NeuroDesk](#) - gitHub
- [FAIMS 3.0](#) - gitHub

Simple Solutions:

The easiest solution is to create a page about your project on an existing website, especially one that already has visitors, like your institution or the ARDC. Some options include:

- Use your ARDC project page as your single landing page for your project. The ARDC is happy to keep that page updated regularly with your input, and you can use it as the main webpage if it suits your needs. Request updates via comms@ardc.edu.au. The ARDC Communication team can provide a Google Doc of your webpage content for you to track changes for updates.
- Create a project page at your institution or organisation
- You can list your ARDC co-investment on your university, department or organisation's profile page.

If you do want to create a website...

You can use website builders like GitHub, Canva, Squarespace, Wix, WordPress etc to create a website, often for free but domain names and hosting will add on cost. Your institution/department/organisation may also be able to help.

Mailing list

We recommend creating a mailing list. This will collect all the people interested in your project in one place. It is also an 'owned' channel - you control it, you have the data, and you don't rely on someone else or an algorithm on social media to reach your target audience.

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Tools

Simplest: a contact group in your email

Simple: Use Google Forms, which creates a Google Sheet. Link to the form to request people to register their interest in the project. Google forms create a Google Sheet with all the details from the form, so it's easy to use.

Ask a bit about the person registering, e.g. organisation, field, job title, location.

A Google [group](#) may be another option.

External tool: Mailchimp

- free up to 2000 contacts.
- Form to gather information about your audience, e.g. discipline, interests, institution, position
- Contact manager so you can download information about your audience
- [More information](#)

Note: be mindful of adhering to the relevant privacy policy when collecting and/or using personal information for your project. See, for example, the [ARDC's Privacy Policy](#).

Social media

If social media isn't your thing, don't attempt to create and maintain your own LinkedIn profile. Instead, reach out to relevant organisations/people to share your announcements/milestones for you.

For example, the ARDC has [LinkedIn](#), [YouTube](#), with an audience of those interested in research data and infrastructure. We can share your message with these ready-made audiences.

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LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a good channel for industry, business and senior influencers, like directors of organisations. We are seeing more engagement from researchers as well, with the demise of Twitter as a trusted social media platform.

Events

Before deciding whether to participate or hold an event, consider your communication purpose:

1. Raise awareness

If you are trying to raise awareness with specific audiences about your project, then events are a great option.

2. Convince someone

Are you trying to convince someone to invest in your product, or change their behaviour significantly? Then a more personal approach would be more effective than speaking at an event. For example, securing support from a research institution for your project will be most effective via a small meeting, rather than a talk to a research division.

Types of Events

Take a look at your list of target audiences, and consider which events you will find them at. You may wish to ask a few people you know from the target audience which events they would recommend.

Examples include:

- Domain-specific conferences - share your project via a presentation, poster, or booth
- Organise webinars on specific topics of interest for your audience
- ARDC events - speak to your ARDC liaison about what may be appropriate, or take a look at [our fortnightly newsletter](#) for ideas.
- eResearch Australasia
- Events at your institution, or those of your partner institutions

- Early career researcher events and professional development
- Domain or profession-specific community events
- TED talks - if you have an idea, pitch it to your local TED talk committee

The key to having impact through events: Ensure you have an action for those interested in your talk/etc to take at the end, for example, sign up to your mailing list, become a beta tester, register for an upcoming webinar.

The Media

Being mentioned in the media can get you broad attention to your project, but you will need a good story to tell, and experienced media communications people to assist you. The media is also an excellent way to get the attention of influencers and policy makers in government.

Who to ask for help: The best way to proactively get media attention is to work with your institutional, departmental or organisational communications team. They can work with you to write a media release and then use their established relationships to try to get coverage. The ARDC communication team is also happy to assist.

Timing: If you want media attention, you need to start work at least a month before a journal paper is published or your product launches to ensure you're ready.

[The Conversation](#) is a specific channel you can explore, which has a large audience and is often republished in major news publications like ABC news, The New York Times, The Guardian, The Washington Post, and CNN.

The best time to pitch an article idea to The Conversation is BEFORE an academic journal article has been published, OR in the lead up to launching your research infrastructure. Before embarking on this, please read the [requirements](#) for becoming an author for The Conversation (i.e. you must be currently employed as a researcher or academic with a university or research institution). We then recommend that, as soon as you have a launch or publish date, you work on a 'pitch' with the [ARDC communications team](#) and/or your institutional communications team. Here's a guide to [pitching to The Conversation](#).

[360info](#) based at Monash University, is a similar outlet to The Conversation.

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Harness the power of your project partners

Your project partners are likely to have established communication channels that reach your target audience. We recommend considering the following steps to engage and harness the power of your project partner communication channels:

1. Find out who the relevant communication teams are from each of your partners
2. Introduce yourself and your project, and share your pitch and upcoming communication milestones
3. You may ask about newsletters that are sent to audiences you are trying to reach - find out if you could provide relevant events or news, and when submissions are due for them.
4. Make it easy for communication teams to share information about your project. For example, create a stakeholder communication pack. Here is an example of a [stakeholder communication pack prepared for the ARDC Planet Research Data Commons](#).

Influencer marketing

This is a good option when your project is highly relevant to a specific domain of research or practitioners. It allows you to piggyback on key influencers' established networks, influence and trust.

Process:

- Grow a group of 'champions/influencers/advocates' who are well known in your target audience communities.
- Give them a title of PROJECT CHAMPION or similar.
- Empower this small group of people to share your project with those they speak to.
- Give them tools to do so - eg. a slide for presentations, social media to share, hard copy fliers. You may do this via a small email list or Google group.

Communities, Societies, Associations and Groups

Domain or profession-specific communities, societies, associations and groups are a good way to reach researchers. Consider organising an event with one of these groups, or speaking at a conference. You may also be able to submit content for newsletters.

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ARDC communication channels available to ARDC co-investment projects

These are the ARDC communication channels. Please contact the comms@ardc.edu.au to coordinate communications across our channels.

[ARDC Connect newsletter](#) - share news (e.g. testing started), events, resources (inc. webinar recordings), and job opportunities

[ARDC project webpage](#) - can be updated anytime

[ARDC feature article](#) - share important milestones, launches, outcomes

[ARDC case study](#) - demonstrate impact

ARDC social media - [LinkedIn](#), [YouTube](#)

[ARDC-run events](#), including [Communities of Practice](#).

OTHER CHANNELS

There may be other digital communication channels you participate in where your audience gathers. For example, a Slack channel, Teams channel, or a listserv or Google group.

Communication tools/assets

Tools/assets you can use to communicate via the channels listed above. It is important to maintain consistent branding across all media channels - logo, font, style guide (may not be needed for every project).

- Websites: ARDC and its partner networks
- Project pages on partner websites
- Newsletter articles
- Targeted emails (individual, or via a mailing list)

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- Case studies
- Presentation slides
- Printed Promotional materials (e.g. leaflets)
- Video - recordings of webinars, promotional videos, instructional videos
- Social media - assets (images, text, banners) / posts
- Media - industry publications / blogs, podcasts
- Communications channels of other organisations (eg e-newsletters)

Create Your Communication Plan

Now that you have looked at the phases of your project, project milestones, and communication channels and tactics, you're ready to craft your communication plan. The table below will help you plan what communication activities you want to take for each target audience to reach your communication goals.

The plan is designed to be a living document, updated as you work through your project and come up with communication ideas.

Milestone	Frequency/timing	Comms activity	Related communication objective	Goal of activity	Target audience/s	Key message/s	Communication tool/ channel	Responsibility	KPI / Results
Project launch	June 2023	e.g. Launch project via ARDC article	Build awareness with research community about the project	Share news of launch with the research community	Research community Stakeholders Future end users	Use X to do X faster/better/safer	Share via: ARDC website ARDC newsletter ARDC social media Our website Our social media Host-institution channels	Project team	# of users # website views
Project Launch		e.g. Website landing page		Share news of launch on our website					
Ongoing activity	Publish monthly	Blog/article updates		Frequent updates on the project to keep audience	Future end-users/Researchers	We're building a data asset that will accelerate research	Share via: Website Email update Social media Share with ARDC comms team		# of users # website views # of enquiries # new partners

Milestone	Frequency/ timing	Comms activity	Related communicatio n objective	Goal of activity	Target audience/s	Key message/s	Communication tool/ channel	Responsibility	KPI / Results
				engaged					
Add more rows and information									

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Evaluate Your Communication

- Set up Google alerts for your project name to track any online mentions. [Set it up now.](#)
- Record external mentions of your projects
- Record journal paper mentions and citations
- If you have a website, enable [Google analytics](#), which will help you measure the impact of your communication activities, and discover how people are learning about your project
- Use the KPI/Results column in the communication plan to track your impact metrics.

Acknowledging the ARDC

ARDC projects must acknowledge ARDC co-investment and support provided by the ARDC on presentations, brochures, project outputs and websites. See the ARDC [Acknowledgement guidelines](#).

Please send all artwork and communications to the ARDC communications team to review via comms@ardc.edu.au.

Resources

Webinars from the Research Data Alliance on '**How to get attention for Research Project Outputs**', presented by Jennifer Gibson, Executive Director of Dryad in the UK:

[Part 1](#) describes how to intervene in the research lifecycle to promote different behaviours (including data-sharing) and nurture associated benefits for research and society.

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[Part 2](#) is a deep-dive into tactics for connecting with the communities we seek, where they are, and in their language how to build awareness and create engagement in the academic community. [*highly recommended*]

Deep dive into your audiences with this useful guide for startup marketing. The guide provides a process for investigating your audience/customers 'pain points' so you can create messaging that shows how you will solve their problems. [View the toolkit](#).

[Communication Toolkit for Research Infrastructures](#), created by RI-VIS, an EU Horizon 2020 funded project designed to increase the visibility of European research infrastructures (RIs) to new communities in Europe and beyond. The Resources section is helpful.

Science Gateways Community Institute (US) has [useful resources](#).

How the ARDC Communication and Marketing Team Can Assist

We are happy to help with any questions that arise from this communication toolkit.

- For significant milestones (i.e. launches), we can write a draft joint announcement/media release/article. We need 6 weeks notice for this, so we can schedule a time to discuss it, seek external quotes, and allow time for internal/partner review.
- We can provide advice on communication tools
- We can share events and content via our newsletter and LinkedIn
- We approve use of the ARDC logo and acknowledgements.

Please contact us via comms@ardc.edu.au.

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You've Completed the Toolkit!

Congratulations on completing the ARDC Communication Toolkit!

In this toolkit you have:

- Described your project key communication goals, messages and audience
- Investigated different communication tools and tactics
- Crafted a communication plan around the phases and milestones of your project
- Reviewed tips for evaluating your communication.

There is no requirement from the ARDC to complete this toolkit. We are however, happy to assist you if you have any questions, or would like feedback on your communication plan. We would love to support your communication activities.

We'd like to hear from you! How did you use this toolkit? What did you like about it? What could be improved? Let us know comms@ardc.edu.au.

Contact us. If you have questions about the content of this toolkit, or would like assistance, please contact the ARDC Communication and Marketing team via comms@ardc.edu.au.